

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

BLOCKCHAIN AND EDUCATION. PERSPECTIVES ON CONNECTING WITH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the possibilities of using blockchain technology in education. It describes the technology, its features, the structure of databases formed. The fields of application of the technology are defined. Its advantages associated with a distributed register, transaction security, transparency of actions, anonymity are considered from the point of view of educational needs. The problem of trust, reliability, security and validity is raised. Examples of effective use of blockchain in education are given. A new blockchain system that operates on a linearly scalable consensus mechanism is presented. The importance of blockchain technology for global education, intra- and inter-country comparisons of Sustainable Development Goal 4, Global Action Agenda for ESD, is justified. The possibility of increasing the utility of blockchain when combined with artificial intelligence technology is presented.

Keywords: blockchain, artificial intelligence, education, SDGs, big data, trustworthiness.

Blockchain is a fundamentally new reliable technology for storing records, which could fundamentally change the way modern databases are formed and stored in various fields. Now it is one of the most widely discussed and open technologies. This technology opens wide horizons for the implementation of new high-tech projects.

Blockchain technology was proposed in 2008 by Satoshi Nakamoto. It took about 10 months to make it technically feasible and implement it. And in 2009, it was used for the first time in the form we know today.

The word "blockchain" is made up of two "blocks" and "chain", and translates as "blockchain". The advantages of this technology are clear from the description of its algorithm:

1. High security of transactions.
2. Transparency of transfers and movements of funds.
3. Preservation of anonymity with full access to all stored information [2].

Blockchain is a technology that uses a distributed database.

Blockchain can be used wherever it is necessary to ensure distributed and anonymous transactions while ensuring a high level of security, but without the need for a third trusted party to be involved in the transactions [10].

It is necessary to clearly understand the advantages of using a distributed storage of information.

A system or blockchain is an ordered database that stores all information on all computers interacting with the network. The technology allows you to store information, a registry of all transactions and contracts made, with a time stamp, reference to the previous block and other necessary data, containing data about all participants. The essence and principle of the blockchain is as follows: there are blockchain users in the system who are able to see all the transactions taking

place; the whole system consists of blocks that are connected to each other. That is, it is impossible to change, delete, damage one or more blocks - it requires the "permission" of all blocks in the system; when a transaction is made, only the recipient gets the result, but all users see the transaction; when a transaction is made, each block processes this information and, if all blocks get the same result, the transaction forms a new block in the system [6;12].

The use of blockchain is a step forward for the state in both technological and financial development. Blockchain is useful in areas where there are many participants in the process and few intermediaries. A big advantage of blockchain is that it is publicly available. All participants can see the blocks and the transactions stored in them. This does not mean that everyone can see the actual content of the transaction; it is protected by your private key.

Blockchain is a technology useful for educational organizations sharing a distributed database in an environment where there is a level of mistrust between them. Educational organizations don't just mean individual entities operating in the marketplace or companies participating in the same conduction chain. It can also be departments of one large organization, for example, operating in different countries. Mistrust means that one entity will not allow another to make changes to its records in the database. Similarly, when learning how to use educational products, one user does not have to take for granted what another user claims, since each may have different economic or political interests [9].

Blockchain eliminates the need for trusted intermediaries and experts by allowing a large number of students who do not trust each other to make changes directly to databases.

No central access controller is needed to verify transactions and authenticate their source. Instead, the definition of a transaction is extended to include proof

of authorization and proof of validity. As a result, transactions can be independently verified and processed by each node that maintains a copy of the database.

Blockchain is a digital cluster for records and changes on the network; not only records of financial transactions, but any other existing value-any type of information in the world-can be programmed into them.

The merits of blockchain for education are particularly evident in situations involving student transactions [3].

The advantage of blockchain is that transactions can be performed jointly by multiple people, without risk to either party. This blockchain feature makes it possible to securely execute a study-product-payment agreement without resorting to the use of an intermediary. Processing student payments is usually a labor-intensive process and can involve the student himself, parents, scholarship agencies, financial institutions, governments, and educational institutions.

Technology allows multiple individuals (teachers) to enter student records simultaneously, and in the case of inclusive education, specialists and counselors can do so as well. The sequence of records allows you to build a history of events, information on the dynamics of progress, personal learning trajectories, as well as to collect personal portfolios, the history of the development of the college (school, university), its teaching staff, its achievements - for their analysis, rapid response to stresses arising in the system, taking action. We emphasize that due to the spatial remoteness of individual campuses, it can be very difficult to quickly detect accumulating problems [10].

The use of blockchain in higher education makes it possible to keep records of degrees, certificates and diplomas, to digitize accounting data without the need to verify them through an intermediary. Blockchain can also be used to accredit educational institutions, which is a complex process in many countries, allowing them to verify the quality or qualifications of a faculty member. Blockchain's ability to improve record-keeping also makes it a natural approach to solve intellectual property management problems, for example by using blockchain to determine the uniqueness of an idea or invention or to register assets, copyrights and patents.

University diplomas received by a faculty member, using blockchain, could create a virtual transcript or record of all educational achievements over a lifetime.

A verifiable lifelong transcript would reduce the number of fake resumes, make it easier to transfer students between universities, reduce the overhead associated with verifying records, and make moving between states and countries less complicated.

Blockchain makes it possible to control academic content and the quality of educational programs, identify organizational and faculty credentials, and form universal rules and approaches.

We describe a new blockchain system that operates on a linearly scalable consensus mechanism, includes a selection method that validates the shard by voting shares, and has scalable randomness generation

using a random check function and a delay check function [7]. The proposed method for creating a fully scalable, provably secure and energy efficient blockchain, through the use of a new consensus protocol, sharding and distributed randomness generation provides an opportunity to qualitatively improve the capabilities of the technology used in education. Methods of creating such a blockchain improve already existing mechanisms of blockchain functioning and have practical value of using the blockchain distributed database for educational needs, in particular, identification and accounting of student progress, automatic issuance of diplomas and certificates, conducting tests, attracting investments. The technology is promising in the informatization of education in distance learning.

We also link the prospects of blockchain use in education with the process of promotion of individual countries in the field of Sustainable Development Goal 4, in the implementation of the Global Action Program on Education for Sustainable Development and the Roadmap for the implementation of this Program, which include big data. Blockchain allows the creation of common global educational services and resources and is itself conceptualized as a consequence of the formation of the Global Education Space - the interaction of national educational systems, the conditions of their development and existence in the modern globalization paradigm of civilizational development, as a result of which the differences between different educational systems are reduced. The technology uses a software module that processes the information content of ordered interconnected data blocks as a whole, maintaining the integrity of the global education space. The ultimate goal of the blockchain system functioning in the global education space is the circulation of reliable information; structuring the phases of implementation of new technological solutions in education, which determines the quality of the national education system; its advancement in the field of innovation for SDG 4 [5;8].

In general, blockchain technology allows to solve the problems of authentication, verification and management. It can be used as a tool for the development of educational organizations of a locality, region, country, several countries in the context of sustainable development goals.

Blockchain technology has special capabilities when combined with artificial intelligence, which can "intelligently" analyze, design, and predict development situations [1]. AI can increase the efficiency of using the data accumulated in the blockchain, and blockchain can justify why the AI made a particular decision. Unlike centralized AI variants, blockchain technology creates transparent, decentralized networks; if it aims for widespread data distribution, it becomes the basis for decentralized artificial intelligence. Combining blockchain and artificial intelligence makes it possible to create systems for backing up sensitive and very valuable personal data, ensuring a high level of security, including, for example, personalized recommendations. The combination of these two technologies will allow data to be used in ways previously thought impossible [11].

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